

SURROGATIVE MATERNITY IN UZBEKISTAN'S LEGISLATION

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Abstract

This article discusses surrogacy, its types, and regulation in Uzbekistan's legislation. Additionally, it addresses the challenges of regulating surrogacy and examines a map of countries that either permit or prohibit it by law. The article also presents legislative proposals based on foreign experience.

Keywords: surrogative maternity, surrogate mother, commercial, altruistic, biological mother, legal mother.

Nowadays, words like “surrogate motherhood” and “surrogate mother” are occasionally heard. Although these concepts emerged on a global scale in the last century, this concept and practice have only recently begun to enter our country. So, what is surrogate motherhood?

“Surrogate motherhood is a form of assisted reproductive technology in which three people participate in pregnancy and childbirth: a genetic (biological) father - a person who has provided his sperm for fertilization and agreed to assume paternal responsibilities after the birth of the child; a genetic (biological) mother - a person who has provided her egg for fertilization and agreed to assume maternal responsibilities after the birth of the child; a surrogate mother - a woman of

childbearing age who agrees to carry and give birth to a child (embryo) from the genetic parents, either voluntarily or for compensation, and who does not claim maternal rights to this child. After the birth of a child, the genetic (biological) parents are registered as legal parents”¹.

It should be noted that surrogacy is not regulated by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Strange, social relations exist, but they are not regulated!

In fact, surrogate motherhood can take 2 forms:

a) traditional - a surrogate mother is also considered a biological mother.

b) a surrogate mother does not have the status of biological and legal motherhood.

Surrogacy is prohibited in some countries of the world, in some it is regulated by law, in others it is unclear, that is, such a social relationship has not yet appeared.

For example, Russia, Ukraine, and neighboring Kazakhstan are considered legal under their legislation, and even Ukraine has advanced in inviting surrogate mothers to other countries.

Uzbekistan, some countries of South America, and some states of the USA have not yet been legally regulated.

In 80 percent of the African continent, Mongolia, it is shown under uncertain conditions. It is prohibited by law in China and some Islamic countries².

However, there are two other forms of surrogacy:

1. Commercial - where surrogate motherhood is offered for a fee.

2. Altruistic - voluntary, where surrogate motherhood is offered free of charge for couples who cannot become parents.

¹ <https://www.gov.uk/legal-rights-when-using-surrogates-and-donors>

² https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Map-showing-the-current-legal-status-of-surrogacy-in-Europe_fig2_366673807

In some countries, both types are legally prohibited or permitted, or only the altruistic form is allowed. For example, in countries such as Australia, India, and Canada, the second form is permitted.

In fact, currently some clinics in Uzbekistan are offering and carrying out surrogacy for a fee, meaning there are surrogate mothers in Uzbekistan.

Even if surrogacy is carried out, it would be incorrect to prosecute this action under *Article 135 of the Criminal Code*, because payment is made for bringing a child into the world, not for human trafficking. In general, the legislation does not specify who is the legal mother in these relations.

Now the question arises:

Why, despite the introduction and implementation of social relations, are they still not regulated by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan?

Firstly, the question arises of which of the two types of surrogacy to recognize or reject, and requires medical and legal investigation. For example, what prevents a surrogate mother from becoming a legal mother when she is traditionally a paid or free surrogate mother?

Secondly, to determine the legal position, it is necessary to forecast the norm and its result for the long term. If this relationship is legally permitted, what will be its consequences, and what if it is prohibited?

Thirdly, it is also important where surrogacy is carried out.

To summarize the above:

Surrogacy as a social relationship exists in Uzbekistan, but is not regulated by law.

- Proposing surrogacy and being a surrogate mother is not prohibited by law and is not permitted.

- In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a woman who is a surrogate mother is not prohibited by law from giving the child to the biological father and biological mother after giving birth.

In order to prevent the above confusion and problems and regulate social relations, it is proposed to reflect in the legislation of Uzbekistan the concept of surrogacy and contractual aspects of surrogacy, and according to the legislation, we believe that aspects of compensation for moral damage, that is, how it is regulated in cases of stillbirth, should be reflected in the legislation.

References:

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